

TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE PRONUNCIATION THROUGH MOVEMENT AND GESTURE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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***Abstract.** The study examines the teacher and primary school learners gesture employed in teaching and learning suprasegmental features of second language (L2) pronunciation such as syllabification, word stress, and rhythm. Children performed vocabulary recall and translation tests at 3 days, 2 months, and 6 months post-learning. Both gesture and movement enhanced children's test performance compared with non-enriched learning. Benefits of gesture and movement persisted up to 6 months after training and occurred for both concrete and abstract words.*

***Keywords.** Intonation, individual sounds, minimal pairs, syllable, body language, verbal material.*

Introduction. It might seem silly to talk about using your body to teach and learn pronunciation, given that you can hardly pronounce without using your lungs, vocal cords, tongue, lips, jaw, etc. However, this article gives tips on using other parts of your body to illustrate what your tongue etc should do. Parts of your body that you can use this way include:

- a finger (e.g. putting one index finger in front of your mouth to show the “Quiet please” meaning of “sh” in “sheep”)
- a hand (e.g. rapidly opening a fist and spreading your fingers to show plosive sounds such as “p” in “pan”)
- an arm (e.g. beating out the syllables of a word, with a much more dramatic up and down motion on the stressed syllable, or waving a hand up and down more dramatically to show extreme intonation in “No???? Really????”)

- your face (e.g. screwing up your face in disgust to show a typical time when we make the sound “er/ ur/ ir”)
- your whole body (e.g. miming a really dramatic sneeze, including leaning back beforehand, to illustrate the sound “ch” in “chess”)

To put all that another way, this means you can use almost any part of your body to demonstrate and help produce stress, intonation or individual sounds. The sections below explain how to do so in more detail.

Teachers probably use gestures most often to demonstrate stress, e.g. to contrast “an INcrease” with “to inCREASE”. Perhaps the most common way of doing this is by pretending to hit a drum and hitting the stressed syllable with a longer and harder stroke than the others. Other possibilities include:

- actually hitting your other hand only on the stressed syllable (only “hitting the air” for the other syllables, e.g. air hit, air hit, air hit, hit your hand, air hit for “communiCAtion”)
- opening up the hand more and opening up the hand less (pinching all the fingers together and then opening it up in a kind of flashing gesture, with the fingers really spread apart for a stressed syllable, e.g. big flash, small flash, small flash for “COMMunist”)
- raising your hand on the stressed syllable as you count off the number of syllables (e.g. first finger up, second finger up as you raise your hand and then third finger up with the hand back down for “unUSual”).

Another common use of body language is to show intonation. I agree with those who say there is little point trying to teach actual intonation patterns, especially to those like me who can’t even tell if a musical note is going up or down. As well as using the gestures above and getting primary school learners to copy them as you elicit, present and correct word stress, minimal pairs, etc, you can also continue to use them during practice activities. For example, if you are doing a minimal pairs game such as Stations (primary school learners to run and

touch two walls with different sounds written on them), you can accompany the first few prompt sounds and words with gestures and then mix up using just the sounds with using just the gestures.

Conclusion. We identified long-term benefits of gesture and movement on primary school children's learning of novel L2 vocabulary. Gesture and movement strategies were tested systematically using large sample sizes of children in an applied, naturalistic school environment. Gesture enrichment improved children's ability to translate novel vocabulary, compared with non-enriched learning. These benefits were present immediately following L2 training and persisted up to 2 to 6 months after training had ended. Gesture enrichment was, however, not more beneficial than movement in terms of L2 retention. We conclude that self-performed gestures and movement may serve as equally beneficial strategies for the learning of foreign language vocabulary in primary school contexts. Conventional primary school teaching strategies such as listening to verbal material may therefore be improved by implementing pictures or gestures into vocabulary learning tasks.

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